

Role of Parental Encouragement Initiatives on Mental Health of Secondary School Students in Meerut District, Uttar Pradesh

Santosh Kumar Sharma¹ & Renu Sharma²

1. Associate Professor, Faculty of Education, Motherhood University, Roorkee

2. Research Scholar, Faculty of Education, Motherhood University, Roorkee

Received : 25/04/2024

1st BPR : 04/05/2024

2nd BPR : 15/05/2024

Accepted : 26/05/2024

Abstract

The study examined the Parental Encouragement in relation to Mental Health of Secondary School Students. Survey method was employed and the investigators used stratified random sampling technique. The study was conducted on 200 students District Meerut of Uttar Pradesh. Parental Encouragement Scale developed by Dr. R.R. Sharma and Mental Health Battery (MHB) developed by Dr. Alpana Sen Gupta were used as the tool. T test and correlation was used as the statistical technique for analysing the data.

Keywords: Parental Encouragement, Mental Health, Secondary School, Relationship.

Introduction

Parents always want the best for their child and always want their child to live a better life than they did. Parents provide as many resources as they can, but this can also be negative to the child's education in sometime. Parental encouragement is the inspiration or extra-boosting given by the parents to the children for their active involvement in academic life. Parental encouragement plays an important role in the formation of life of children. It also enables them to face the future challenges of life. It involves a number of things like deep understanding of developmental process and learning of temperaments, intelligent, personality patterns, inter personal action and socialization etc. Not all learning happens in school; some takes place at home. To ensure those students are encouraged or motivated to learn at home, educators must involve parents.

Parents are the primary designers of a child's life and are in charge of determining the personality and intellectual abilities of the child. One of the most crucial elements in a child's growth and development is parental encouragement. In order to increase the likelihood that further instances of excellent conduct will occur, parents should treat their children with care, concern, approbation, and guidance (Sharma, 1988). This is referred to as "parental encouragement." Encouragement fosters an atmosphere that is favourable to good self-acceptance and self-esteem (Thoresen, 2014). A close-knit, loving relationship between parents and children is seen as a reliable indicator of adolescents' life satisfaction.

A healthy parent-child relationship fosters students' sense of security by helping them learn to trust their parents in times of need. As a result, students have a positive outlook on life and are less likely to experience mental health issues. Most kids view their parents as the most crucial source of help, moral guidance, sense of community, and socialisation. Parental involvement in a child's life reduces the likelihood of loneliness, anxiety, and suicide ideation (Pengpid & Peltzer, 2018).

Literature Review

Narad, A. and Singh, A. K. (2020), conducted a study on a sample of 200 senior secondary school girls of Jainpur and Azamgarh District of Uttar Pradesh to know the influence of parental encouragement

on self-confidence. It was found that positive correlation existed between self-confidence and parental encouragement of senior secondary school girls.

Kaur, J. (2013), studied about mental health of adolescents as a correlate to parental encouragement. The main objectives of the investigation were to see the influence of gender and locality on mental health and parental encouragement of adolescents as well as to find out the relationship between these two variables. The results had shown that there existed gender differences regarding the mentioned aspects. Again, no significant difference was found in the mean scores of mental health between urban and rural adolescents. But, in case of parental encouragement, difference was found on the basis of locality. Also, a significant relationship was found between mental health and parental encouragement of adolescents.

Objectives

1. To study the Parental Encouragement of male and female secondary school students.
2. To study the Mental Health of male and female secondary school students.
3. To find out relationship between parental encouragement and mental health of secondary school students.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to parental encouragement.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to mental health.
3. There is a positive relationship between parental encouragement and mental health of secondary school students.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive method because only this method could be appropriate for the present research problem. The survey method gathers data from a relatively large number of cases at a particular time. The sample for the present study consists of 200 secondary school students were selected by random sampling technique. The sample collected from different secondary schools of Class 9th in district Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh and random sampling technique were used for the sample subject. Parental Encouragement Scale developed by Dr. R.R. Sharma and Mental Health Battery (MHB) developed by Dr. Alpana Sen Gupta were used as the tool.

Data Analysis

Table No.- 1.1:
**Frequency Distribution of Male and Female Respondents
in Respect to Parental Encouragement**

Levels	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage	Total
High	47	44.76	33	34.74	80
Average	36	34.29	42	44.21	78
Low	22	20.95	20	21.05	42
	N=105	100	N=95	100	N=200

Source: Calculated by Researcher

From the above table no.-1.1, it is clear that 47 i.e. 44.76 percent male students belong to high level of parental encouragement and 42 i.e. 44.21 percent female students belongs to average level of parental encouragement. So it clear that male students highly encourage by parents than female students.

Table No.- 1.2: Frequency Distribution of Male and Female Respondents in Respect to Mental Health.

Dimensions	Level of Mental Health	Gender			
		Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage
Emotional Stability	High	45	42.86	35	36.84
	Average	38	36.19	41	43.16
	Low	22	20.95	19	20.00
Over-all Adjustment	High	39	37.14	42	44.21
	Average	46	43.81	35	36.84
	Low	20	19.05	18	18.95
Autonomy	High	43	40.95	39	41.05
	Average	38	36.19	36	37.50
	Low	24	22.86	20	21.05
Security-Insecurity	High	46	43.81	37	38.95
	Average	37	35.24	41	43.16
	Low	22	20.95	17	17.89
Self-Concept	High	41	39.05	40	42.11
	Average	45	42.86	37	38.95
	Low	19	18.10	18	18.95
Intelligence	High	45	42.86	37	38.95
	Average	40	38.10	40	42.11
	Low	20	19.05	18	18.95
N=500		N=105	100%	N=95	100%

Source: Calculated by Researcher

Table No.- 1.3: Consolidated Value of Male & Female Respondents in Respect to Mental Health.

Levels	Male	Average	Percentage	Female	Average	Percentage	Total
High	259	43	40.95	230	38	40.00	81
Average	244	41	39.05	230	38	40.00	79
Low	127	21	20.00	110	19	20.00	40
		N=105	100		N=95	100	N=200

Source: Calculated by Researcher

Table No.- 1.2 shows mental health dimensions - Emotional Stability, Over-all Adjustment, Autonomy, Security-Insecurity, Self-Concept and Intelligence. Maximum male and female students belongs to average and high mental health level of all dimensions. It is clear from table no.-1.3 that maximum male (43) and female (38) students belongs to high level of mental health.

Hypothesis-1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to parental encouragement.

Table No.- 1.4: Calculation of Significant Difference between Male and Female Secondary School Students in Respect to Parental Encouragement.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	D.F	Std. Error	t Value	Significance Level
Male Students	105	35.00	12.53	198	9.65	0.35	Not Significant
Female Students	95	31.67	11.06				

Source: Calculated by Researcher

Table no.- 1.4 shows that data related to the parental encouragement between male and female secondary school students has been analysed. Based on the analysis of data related to parental encouragement between male and female secondary school students, the mean value was 35.00 and 31.67 respectively, standard deviation was 12.53 and 11.06 respectively. The calculated value of t is 0.35, which is less than the table value (0.75). Hence, H_{01} hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to parental encouragement in Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh.

Hypothesis-2

H_{02} : There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to mental health.

Table No.- 1.5: Calculation of Significant Difference between Male and Female Secondary School Students in Respect to Mental Health.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	D.F	Std. Error	t Value	Significance Level
Male Students	105	35.00	12.17	198	9.46	0.35	Not Significant
Female Students	95	31.67	10.97				

Source: Calculated by Researcher

Table no.- 1.5 shows that data related to the mental health between male and female secondary school students has been analysed. Based on the analysis of data related to mental health between male and female secondary school students, the mean value was 35.00 and 31.67 respectively, standard deviation was 12.17 and 10.97 respectively. The calculated value of t is 0.35, which is less than the table value (0.74). Hence, H_{02} hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to mental health.in Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh.

Hypothesis-3

H_{03} : There is a positive relationship between parental encouragement and mental health of secondary school students.

Table No.- 1.6: Calculation of Correlation between Parental Encouragement and Mental Health of Secondary School Students.

Parameter	Value
Pearson Correlation Coefficients (r)	1
r^2	1
P Value	0.002231
Covariance	494.33
Statistic	285.40

Source: Calculated by Researcher

Results of the Pearson correlation indicated that there is a significant large positive relationship between parental encouragement and mental health, ($r(1) = 1, p = .002$). Hence, H_{03} hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between parental encouragement and mental health of secondary school students in Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the above mentioned hypotheses and the conclusions drawn from them, it is clear that-

1. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to parental encouragement
2. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in respect to mental health.

3. There is a positive relationship between parental encouragement and mental health of secondary school students in Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh.

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